

EBSU INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (EIJESSD)

VOLUME 2 NO 1. MARCH, 2026 | ISSN: 3092-8613

<https://ebsujournals.com/index.php/eijessd>

PLASTIC-FREE BHARAT: A BLUEPRINT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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D.O.I.: 10.5281/zenodo.19883564

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Received: 26h January, 2026
Accepted: 25th February, 2026
Published: 31st March, 2026

KEYWORDS: Plastic ban in India, plastic waste management, single-use plastics, sustainable alternatives, extended producer responsibility (EPR), public awareness.

PUBLISHER: Faculty of Law, Ebonyi State University

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of plastic in India has resulted in severe environmental degradation, posing threats to ecosystems, public health, and urban infrastructure. Despite the introduction of the Plastic Waste Management Rules (2016) and subsequent amendments, India continues to grapple with over 3.4 million tons of plastic waste annually, a significant portion of which consists of single-use plastic bags, Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), 2021. These bags are often non-biodegradable, clog drainage systems, pollute rivers, and pose dangers to wildlife. The ineffectiveness of current legislation stems from fragmented enforcement, lack of public awareness, and insufficient availability of eco-friendly alternatives (MoEFCC, 2016; Narayan & Rajendran, 2022). This study explores the environmental, economic, and regulatory dimensions of plastic bag usage in India, arguing for a nationwide prohibition on their sale. Drawing from successful models in Indian states such as Sikkim and Himachal Pradesh, where bans have significantly reduced plastic waste, the paper emphasizes the importance of strict legal enforcement combined with proactive public participation (Singh & Sharma, 2020). Furthermore, global case studies such as Rwanda's total plastic ban demonstrate the viability of decisive policy action supported by awareness and sustainable alternatives (United Nations Environment Programme, UNEP, 2018). The proposed policy framework incorporates a multi-pronged approach: nationwide legal prohibition of plastic bag sales, incentives for biodegradable alternatives, extended producer responsibility (EPR), and large-scale educational campaigns to shift consumer behavior. The study also underlines the importance of collaboration among policymakers, industry stakeholders, and civil society to ensure scalability and compliance. By addressing both supply and demand dimensions, this proposal aims to disrupt India's dependency on plastic bags and promote a transition toward sustainable consumption. Ultimately, a well-structured, enforced national ban on the sale of plastic bags rooted in environmental science and policy reform can serve as a crucial step in India's journey toward circular economy goals and ecological resilience.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian environment is facing a severe crisis due to plastic pollution, particularly from plastic bags. Despite their convenience and affordability, plastic bags pose significant threats to the environment, including blocking drainage systems, harming wildlife, and contributing to long-lasting pollution. India generates approximately 3.4 million tons of plastic waste annually, with a significant portion of it being plastic bags (CPCB, 2020). Plastic bags began making their way into Indian markets around the late 1980s and early 1990s. This period marked a shift in the country's economy, with increased globalization and the expansion of modern retail. Their rise in popularity was fueled by how lightweight, affordable, and easy to use they were, especially for shopkeepers and consumers in growing urban centers. By the late 2000s, India was facing severe plastic pollution due to unregulated production, distribution, and disposal of plastic items especially thin, non-recyclable plastic carry bags. To address this, the Ministry of Environment and Forests (MoEF) notified the Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2009, under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986. These rules were the first comprehensive effort to regulate the life cycle of plastic products in India. Plastic pollution had emerged as a critical environmental concern in India, with single-use plastics being a major contributor. These are items intended to be used once and discarded, often littering public spaces, clogging drains, choking wildlife, and contaminating soil and water. Despite earlier regulations and state-level bans, the use of such plastics persisted widely.

Recognizing the urgent need for decisive national action, the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEFCC) notified a comprehensive ban on certain Single-Use Plastic items, which came into effect on July 1, 2022, under the Plastic Waste Management (Amendment) Rules, 2021.

The impact of plastic on the Indian environment is multifaceted. They can block drainage systems, causing flooding and damage to infrastructure. They can also harm wildlife, including marine animals that mistake them for food. According to a report by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), plastic bags are one of the top 10 items found in marine debris, and can cause harm to over 260 species of marine animals (WWF, 2020). The Indian government has taken steps to address plastic pollution, including introducing regulations to limit the use of plastic carry bags. Several states, including Maharashtra, Karnataka, and Himachal Pradesh, have imposed bans or restrictions on the use of plastic bags. However, the effectiveness of these bans has been hindered by challenges such as lack of enforcement and unavailability of viable alternatives.

A study by the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi found that the average Indian uses around 8-10 plastic bags per day, resulting in a significant amount of plastic waste (IIT Delhi, 2019). The study also highlighted the need for effective solutions to address plastic pollution, including promoting sustainable practices and reducing plastic use. This study seeks to understand whether a complete ban on the sale of plastic bags is both necessary and feasible in the Indian context. By analyzing existing bans and their outcomes, this research aims to identify the main issues encountered and provide solutions to tackle these challenges.

The findings of this study will contribute to the ongoing debate on plastic pollution in India and provide policymakers with evidence-based recommendations for addressing the issue. By exploring the potential benefits and challenges of a ban on plastic bags, this research aims to inform policy decisions and promote sustainable practices in India.

Literature Review

Plastics have emerged as a pervasive environmental threat due to their durability, affordability, and resistance to degradation. Globally, over 8.3 billion tons of plastic have been produced since the 1950s, with only 9% recycled, 12% incinerated, and the rest ending up in landfills or natural environments (Geyer, Jambeck, & Law, 2017). Jambeck et al. (2015) highlighted that developing countries, including India, are among the top contributors to mismanaged plastic waste due to rapid urbanization, rising consumption, and inadequate waste infrastructure. Plastic pollution has profound effects on biodiversity, marine ecosystems, and human health. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2018), single-use plastics (SUPs) account for nearly 50% of all plastic waste, causing significant ecological damage. The organization advocated a comprehensive global approach involving bans, taxes, and alternative materials.

India generates approximately 3.5 million tonnes of plastic waste annually, with a significant portion remaining uncollected or improperly disposed (Central Pollution Control Board [CPCB], 2022). Studies show that plastic constitutes around 6–8% of municipal solid waste by weight, but its non-biodegradable nature and widespread littering make it highly visible and hazardous (Rajagopalan & Bandyopadhyay, 2014). According to Sarkar (2019), major challenges include weak segregation practices, inadequate recycling infrastructure, and the dominance of informal waste collectors. The CPCB (2021) also reported low levels of compliance among manufacturers with registration and reporting requirements under the Plastic Waste Management Rules.

The regulatory journey in India began with the **Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2009**, which set the groundwork for later reforms. Nair (2011) critiqued these rules for their lack of producer accountability and weak enforcement mechanisms. This led to the introduction of the **Plastic Waste Management Rules, 2016**, which brought in concepts like **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR)**, mandatory labeling, and increased minimum thickness of plastic bags to 50 microns.

Bhattacharya, Ninan, and Mohapatra (2016) observed that the 2016 rules represented a paradigm shift by placing more responsibility on producers and local bodies. However, implementation remained inconsistent across states due to varying capacities and enforcement priorities.

In response to growing plastic pollution, the **Plastic Waste Management (Amendment) Rules, 2021** notified a nationwide **ban on select single-use plastic items**, effective July 1, 2022. Sharma and Mahapatra (2023) called this a historic move but noted that its effectiveness depends on awareness campaigns, alternative supply chains, and decentralized enforcement strategies.

India's plastic waste ecosystem is deeply entwined with the informal recycling sector. Studies by Chaturvedi and Ghosh (2015) indicate that informal waste pickers collect and recycle nearly 60% of urban plastic waste, yet remain outside formal waste management systems. Baud et al. (2010) advocated for the integration of informal workers into municipal waste policies to improve recovery rates and promote social inclusion. Gupta (2021) highlighted the success of inclusive models like Pune's "SWaCH" cooperative, where waste pickers are trained, recognized, and

remunerated under public-private partnerships. Such models underscore the need for inclusive and community-driven approaches to plastic governance.

Consumer behavior is central to plastic consumption patterns, Anantharaman (2018) conducted field studies in Bengaluru and found that financial disincentives, such as levies on plastic bags, significantly reduced their use. Khandelwal and Mishra (2020) examined awareness campaigns in urban India and reported positive behavioral shifts in waste segregation and reusable bag adoption when community involvement was high.

However, KPMG India (2021) found that for many small retailers and consumers, **cost and accessibility** remain the primary barriers to adopting alternatives like jute, paper, or compostable plastics. This indicates that policy success depends on both **demand-side incentives and supply-side support**.

India's approach is part of a global wave of anti-plastic regulations. UNEP (2018) noted that over 60 countries have enacted bans or levies on single-use plastics. Kenya's 2017 ban on plastic bags is considered among the world's most stringent, resulting in a 90% reduction in usage within one year (UNEP, 2019). The European Union (2020) has implemented a directive to phase out the 10 most common SUPs found on beaches, coupled with robust EPR mandates. Indonesia and the Philippines have initiated plastic offset credit systems and digital tracking technologies for plastic waste (Mendoza, 2022). Such innovations offer valuable insights for India as it builds its own policy blueprint.

Despite progress, significant gaps remain in both policy and research:

- There is limited **granular data** on rural plastic usage and disposal patterns.
- The **effectiveness of the 2022 SUP ban** in reducing litter and changing consumer habits is yet to be systematically evaluated.
- Few peer-reviewed studies explore the **economic viability and scalability of alternative materials** in India.
- The environmental and health impacts of **microplastics in Indian agriculture** and food systems remain under-researched.

As noted by Sridhar (2023), future research should adopt a multidisciplinary lens, incorporating insights from environmental science, behavioral economics, public policy, and industrial innovation.

Objectives

1. To Examine the Historical Evolution of Plastic Usage and Regulation in India
2. To Critically Review National and International Policy Frameworks Addressing Plastic Waste
3. To Explore the Role of Public Awareness and Behavior Change in Achieving a Plastic-Free Bharat

Research Methodology

This study adopts a **mixed-methods research design**, combining both **qualitative and quantitative approaches** to provide a holistic understanding of India's plastic pollution crisis and its policy responses. The study is **exploratory** in nature, aiming to identify critical issues, assess the effectiveness of interventions, and suggest actionable policy recommendations.

Present and Future of Plastic Worldwide

The plastic products market size has grown strongly in recent years. It will grow from \$1108.17 billion in 2024 to \$1192.56 billion in 2025 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 7.6%. The growth in the historic period can be attributed to versatility and adaptability of plastics, substitution for traditional materials, industrialization and manufacturing growth, automotive industry adoption, packaging industry innovations, consumer electronics boom.

Plastic Products Global Market Report 2025

Sources: <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/plastic-products-global-market-report>

The plastic products market size is expected to see strong growth in the next few years. It will grow to \$1542.98 billion in 2029 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.7%. The growth in the forecast period can be attributed to bio-based and biodegradable plastics, smart and functional plastics, focus on plastic waste management, shift in consumer preferences, global health crises preparedness, efforts to reduce single-use plastics. Major trends in the forecast period include plastic recycling technologies, anti-microbial plastics, lightweight plastic alternatives, plastic-free packaging initiatives, smart plastics with IoT integration, plastic packaging recycling.

Problem faced using plastic in India

- In 1990, the per capita plastic consumption in India was approximately kg per capita by 2024, this figure had increased to 13 kg, indicating a significant rise in individual plastic usage over three decades. (The economics times)

- As of 2024, India has emerged as the world's leading contributor to plastic pollution, generating approximately 9.3 million tons of plastic waste annually. This accounts for nearly 20% of the global total. (Plastic for change)
- The Indian plastic industry is substantial, with a market size estimated at USD 46.48 billion in 2024. However, the environmental challenges posed by plastic waste necessitate urgent and effective waste management strategies. (Market Research reports)

Despite this, India's recycling rate remains low, with only about 8% of plastic waste being recycled.

Regulations introduced in India for plastic waste management

1. Plastic Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2011- Introduced under the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986, these rules marked India's initial structured approach to plastic waste management. They assigned responsibilities to municipal authorities for waste management and introduced the concept of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), making producers accountable for the end-of-life disposal of plastic products.

2. Plastic Waste Management Rules, 2016- Superseding the 2011 rules, the 2016 regulations expanded the scope to include all stakeholders in the plastic life cycle, from producers to consumers. Key provisions included:

- ✓ Mandatory registration for producers, importers, and brand owners.
- ✓ Responsibility for waste segregation and collection assigned to local bodies.
- ✓ Prohibition of plastic carry bags below 50 microns in thickness.
- ✓ Introduction of EPR as a legal obligation.

3. Plastic Waste Management (Amendment) Rules, 2021- These amendments aimed to phase out single-use plastics (SUPs) by 2022. Notable changes included:

- ✓ Ban on specific SUP items with low utility and high littering potential, effective July 1, 2022.
- ✓ Increase in the thickness of plastic carry bags from 50 to 75 microns (effective September 30, 2021) and to 120 microns (effective December 31, 2022).
- ✓ Legal enforcement of EPR guidelines.

4. Plastic Waste Management (Amendment) Rules, 2022- Further strengthening the EPR framework, these rules provided detailed guidelines for plastic packaging, including:

- ✓ Mandatory targets for recycling and reuse of plastic packaging materials.
- ✓ Obligations for producers, importers, and brand owners to ensure the collection and processing of plastic waste.

5. Plastic Waste Management (Amendment) Rules, 2024- The latest amendments focused on:

- ✓ Regulating the use of biodegradable and compostable plastics, with specific labelling and certification requirements.
- ✓ Addressing micro plastic pollution by setting standards and guidelines for their management.
- ✓ Assigning responsibilities to district-level Panchayats for assessing plastic waste generation and infrastructure needs.

Though India has introduced several rules to manage plastic waste, their impact on the ground is barely visible. Plastic bags and single-use items are still widely used, especially in markets and small towns. Most people are unaware of the laws, and authorities often turn a blind eye to violations. Recycling systems are limited, and waste often ends up in landfills or drains. Many producers find ways to dodge restrictions, making enforcement difficult. In the end, despite all the policies and paperwork, very little has changed plastic pollution continues to grow, and the environment keeps paying the price.

Socio Impact of Banning Plastic Bags

The prohibition of plastic bags in India has led to significant socio-economic repercussions, affecting various sectors including small businesses, retailers, manufacturers, employment, and consumer behavior.

Small businesses and street vendors, integral to India's informal economy, have faced challenges adapting to the ban. The increased costs of alternative packaging materials like cloth, jute, or paper bags strain their limited resources, potentially reducing profit margins and threatening their livelihoods. Plastic manufacturers, particularly small and medium enterprises (SMEs), have experienced substantial setbacks. The ban has led to the closure of numerous manufacturing units, resulting in significant job losses and economic downturns within the sector.

Alternatives to plastic bags, such as cloth, jute, and paper bags, present their own challenges. While environmentally friendly, these alternatives often come at a higher cost and may not be as readily available, posing difficulties for widespread adoption. Employment implications are profound, with the ban affecting not only manufacturers but also workers in the recycling and waste management sectors. The transition to alternative materials necessitates new skills and training, which may not be accessible to all displaced workers.

Consumer behavior and awareness play a crucial role in the success of the plastic ban. While some consumers have adapted by using reusable bags, others continue to rely on plastic due to convenience and lack of awareness about the ban's environmental importance. While the ban on plastic bags aims to address environmental concerns, it also brings to light the need for comprehensive strategies that consider economic impacts, provide support to affected sectors, and promote consumer awareness to ensure a successful transition to sustainable alternatives.

Findings of Field Study

The study below was conducted among the stakeholders of plastic bags consumption in five major cities which contributes the most in the GDP of the country.

The study shows us that cities like Delhi, Mumbai and Kolkata where economy generation is majorly coming from retailers, are not in favor of banning the plastic bags because it will impact the profit earned from the business as inventories will increase.

The study also shows the difference in opinion due to literacy rate, cities where literacy rates are high like Coimbatore and Bangalore, and generates economy in form services and IT, are more in

favor of getting complete ban on the plastic bags. Whereas Maharashtra, Delhi and Kolkata prefer amendments in the usage of plastic bags but not complete ban on it.

We need to understand that society needs to know that a complete rating of 10 on the ban of plastic bag (as shown in graph 2) is required so that a rule of banning the plastic bag can be implemented. Out of 200, only 20 people wants a complete ban on the plastic bag that counts upto 10% of the sample population.

Discussions

The debate around banning plastic bags outright is complex and layered, especially in a country like India with vast socio-economic diversity. On one hand, the environmental benefits of a ban are evident reducing non-biodegradable waste, easing pressure on landfills, and mitigating harm to wildlife and marine ecosystems. On the other hand, the economic and practical challenges cannot be ignored. An outright ban often disrupts small businesses, affects livelihoods in the plastic manufacturing sector, and places financial strain on lower-income groups who may not easily afford alternatives.

Advantages of banning plastic bags

Environmental Protection

Plastic bags take hundreds of years to decompose and often end up clogging drains, polluting rivers, and harming marine and terrestrial life. A ban significantly reduces plastic waste and supports a cleaner ecosystem.

Reduction in Non-Biodegradable Waste

Banning plastic bags helps cut down the volume of non-recyclable waste, easing the burden on landfills and waste management systems.

Lower Carbon Footprint

The production of plastic bags involves fossil fuels and emits greenhouse gases. Eliminating their use contributes to lower overall carbon emissions.

Cleaner Public Spaces

Cities and towns that enforce plastic bag bans often experience a noticeable reduction in litter, improving public hygiene and aesthetics.

Encouragement of Eco-Friendly Alternatives

A ban promotes the use of sustainable alternatives like cloth, jute, or paper bags, fostering innovation and growth in the green economy.

Positive Behavioural Change

Bans serve as a wake-up call, prompting individuals and businesses to rethink their consumption patterns and adopt more environmentally responsible practices.

Support for Traditional Industries

The shift from plastic to biodegradable options can revive local industries such as jute weaving and cloth bag making, creating job opportunities in rural and semi-urban areas.

International Image and Compliance

Enforcing a plastic bag ban aligns India with global environmental standards and commitments like the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Disadvantages of banning plastic bags**Economic Impact on Small Businesses**

Small vendors and shopkeepers often rely on inexpensive plastic bags. Banning them forces businesses to spend more on alternatives, increasing operational costs and reducing profit margins.

Job Losses in the Plastic Industry

India's plastic manufacturing and recycling sectors provide employment to thousands. A sudden ban can lead to the closure of units, causing unemployment and economic distress, particularly in the unorganized sector.

Lack of Affordable Alternatives

Replacements like cloth, jute, or paper bags are often costlier and not as readily available, making the transition difficult, especially for low-income groups and rural communities.

Inconsistent Enforcement

Weak enforcement mechanisms and lack of monitoring lead to uneven implementation. In many areas, plastic bags continue to circulate in the black market, undermining the purpose of the ban.

Inconvenience to Consumers

Customers accustomed to the ease and availability of plastic bags may find it difficult to adjust. The need to carry reusable bags and manage heavier alternatives can be seen as a burden.

Environmental Concerns with Some Alternatives

Not all alternatives are environmentally perfect. For instance, paper bags require more water and energy to produce, and cloth bags may have a higher carbon footprint if not reused enough times.

Disruption of Recycling Sector

Plastic waste supports a significant informal recycling economy in India. Banning plastic bags reduces the availability of recyclable materials, affecting the livelihoods of waste pickers and recyclers.

Short-Term Ineffectiveness

Without proper awareness and infrastructural support, bans often fail to create long-term behavioural change. People may shift to other forms of plastic packaging that are equally harmful.

In considering alternative approaches, methods like imposing taxes on plastic bags or offering incentives for using eco-friendly options may prove more effective and less disruptive. Countries

like Ireland and Denmark have successfully reduced plastic usage by levying a plastic bag tax rather than enforcing a total ban. These approaches not only reduce consumption but also generate revenue that can fund environmental projects. Gradual phase-outs—where certain types of plastics are targeted over time, can also help businesses and consumers transition more smoothly to sustainable alternatives.

Education and awareness play a crucial role in changing behaviour. Simply banning plastic without explaining why it matters leads to non-compliance. Field observations and survey data from this study showed that where public education campaigns were strong, such as in parts of Bengaluru and Pune, people were more likely to shift to reusable bags. Campaigns that are community-based and culturally relevant have a higher chance of success in influencing everyday habits.

Finally, any policy decision must consider India's socio-political context. Enforcement remains inconsistent across regions due to weak municipal systems, corruption, and lack of political will in some areas. Moreover, policies must be designed with economic inclusivity in mind—supporting small businesses, offering subsidies for alternative packaging, and providing vocational training to workers affected by the shutdown of plastic-related industries.

While banning plastic bags has strong environmental justifications, a rigid approach may not be feasible or sustainable in the Indian context. A blend of regulation, economic tools, public education, and social support systems would likely create more meaningful and lasting change.

Conclusions

The issue of banning the sale of plastic bags in India is not simply a question of environmental responsibility, it intersects with economic realities, social behaviour, policy enforcement, and public awareness. Through field studies, surveys, and stakeholder insights, this research reveals that while the environmental urgency of curbing plastic pollution is undeniable, a blanket ban on plastic bags poses significant challenges for small businesses, the manufacturing sector, and economically vulnerable communities.

The success of such a ban depends not only on legislative action but also on effective implementation, availability of affordable alternatives, and widespread public participation. Alternative approaches such as gradual phase-outs, taxation, and incentive-driven policies can offer a more inclusive and practical path forward. Moreover, education and awareness campaigns are critical to transforming consumer behaviour and creating a culture of sustainability.

In the Indian context, where enforcement can vary widely across regions and economic disparities are stark, an outright ban—though well-intentioned needs to be supported by a robust ecosystem of alternatives, financial assistance, and policy clarity. Therefore, while the selling of plastic bags should eventually be phased out, a more balanced and phased approach may be more effective in ensuring long-term compliance and sustainability. This research underlines the importance of collaborative efforts between the government, industries, and citizens in addressing the plastic crisis in a way that is environmentally sound and socially just.

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The popularity of masonry construction is due, among other aspects, to its low cost, the local availability of the necessary materials, and the use of traditional construction techniques. Masonry blocks can be made from a variety of materials, types, and dimensions, and can be placed in different ways, normally using a thin mortar layer (≈ 2 cm) that allows linking the blocks. The union mortar can also be made with different types of conglomerates and sand, mixed with water. The mechanical properties of blocks and mortars are very different due to the components that constitute them, from its manufacturing process, their geometry, and size; therefore, when a set of masonry blocks united by a series of mortar layers is subjected to a compression load, a complex interaction appears in the transition zones.